

Research Article

Comparative study and morphological plasticity of an Italian and a Chinese population of the protist ciliate *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* (*Hypotrichia*, *Kentrurostylida*) with a mitochondrial genome analysis

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ABSTRACT

Two populations of the kentrurostylid ciliate *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* Chen et al., 2011 were isolated from a brackish wastewater treatment plant, Pisa, Italy and from a nutrient-rich freshwater body, the East Lake, Wuhan, China. The populations were thoroughly investigated for their morphology, focusing on cell body plasticity. The study was supplemented with 18S rDNA phylogenetic analysis and mitogenome sequencing, following the integrative taxonomy approach. The Italian population possesses a great variation in terms of the frontal area, and the numbers of left marginal rows, and dorsal kineties. Additionally, the number of left marginal anlagen and dorsal kineties anlagen varied. For instance, additional small anlagen appeared in the left marginal rows, and two dorsal kineties anlagen derived from a single dorsal kinety. The Wuhan population resembled the type population (originally isolated from Guangzhou, China), differing only by the presence of an extra dorsal kinety. The existence of giant individuals characterized both new populations of *P. erythrina* although with some differences in their respective frequency and features. The 18S rDNA sequences of the Italian, Wuhan, and type populations were identical. Phylogenetic analyses showed that these three populations formed a distinct cluster within the clade containing *P. songi*, *P. parasongi*, and *P. flava*. The structure of the *P. erythrina* mitochondrial genome is also provided. The content of this genome closely resembled *Pseudourostyla cristata*, except for the absence of genes *nadh3* and *nadh6*. Our findings suggest that the Wuhan population represents an intermediate form between the type and Italian populations. The greater morphological plasticity observed in the Italian population underscores the importance of molecular data and integrative analyses in species identification.

1. Introduction

Hypotrich ciliates, with their highly diverse cirral and morphogenetic patterns, play a crucial role in comprehending the systematics and evolutionary relationships among ciliates (Berger, 2004; Foissner et al., 2004; Heber et al., 2014; Omar et al., 2024; Paiva, 2020; Vďačný and Foissner, 2021; Zhang et al., 2024). Recent molecular and morphological studies have greatly advanced our understanding of the evolution and phylogeny of hypotrich ciliates (Berger, 2018; Chae et al., 2022; Kumar and Foissner, 2017; Luo et al., 2022; Paiva, 2020; Song et al., 2022, 2024;

Zhang et al., 2022). However, species identification and discrimination within the Kentrurostylida, which corresponds to the so-called “core urostyloids”, a robust clade found in Paiva (2020), is challenging due to insufficient studies on many of its members.

The kentrurostylid genus *Pseudokeronopsis* was established by Borror and Wicklow (1983) with *P. rubra* as the type species. The genus is defined by the following features: a continuous adoral zone of membranelles, a bicorona of frontal cirri, a midventral complex composed of midventral pairs only, one marginal row of cirri on each side of the cell, the presence of buccal and transverse cirri, and the absence of caudal

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cirri. To date, twelve species have been investigated, and all their characteristics fit within the genus definition. Among these species, *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* was first isolated by Chen et al. (2011) from the Pearl River estuary in Guangzhou, China, with data on the morphology, morphogenesis, 18S rDNA sequence and putative secondary structures of the type population (hereafter referred to as “GUP”). Subsequently, *P. erythrina* was further analysed for its metabolism, chemical defense, transcriptome, and actin gene. It is also the first recorded member of kentrustylid ciliates hosting a *Rickettsiales* bacterium (Anesi et al., 2016; Buonanno et al., 2017; Castelli et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2020; Yi et al., 2016).

Despite the wealth of knowledge accumulated, several intriguing aspects of *P. erythrina* remained unexplored. In this study, we isolated two new populations of *P. erythrina* from distinct environments: a brackish wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) near Pisa, Italy (hereafter referred to as “ITP”), and a freshwater lake in Wuhan, China (referred to as “WUP”). These new isolates provided an opportunity to investigate the species further, revealing previously undocumented phenomena in kentrustylids, i.e., gigantism and cannibalism, which is mostly found in oxytrichids (Dawson, 1919; Foissner et al., 2002; Giese and Alden, 1938; Kamra and Sapra, 1994; Omar et al., 2023; Wicklow, 1988) and only sporadically in other ciliate groups such as peniculids, colpodeans, tetrahymenids, and heterotrichids (de Puytorac et al., 1992; Devi, 1964; Foissner, 1987, 2013; Foissner et al., 2002; Foissner and O'Donoghue, 1990; Giese, 1938; Kidder et al., 1940; Kuhlmann, 1993; Lennartz, 1982; Pierce et al., 1978). Moreover, we observed a remarkable intraspecific morphological variation within ITP. Therefore, in the present paper, we offer an update on the current knowledge of *P. erythrina* with new insights into its morphology, morphogenesis, intraspecific and intrapopulation variation of the ciliary structure, and position in 18S rDNA and phylogenomic trees. The discovery of notable morphological variations, gigantism, and cannibalism within ITP challenges the existing criteria used for the species identification within the genus *Pseudokeronopsis*.

Finally, previous research has not provided comprehensive genomic information for *P. erythrina*. Our work addresses this gap by providing fundamental genomic data. Based on the analysis of 18S rDNA, we hypothesize that the high morphological plasticity observed in ITP is influenced by the complex and dynamic environment of the wastewater treatment plant. However, further research is required to explore the evolutionary processes affecting aquatic organisms in such complex environments.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample collection, observation, and terminology

The Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* was isolated from activated sludge collected from an industrial WWTP managed by Consorzio Cuoio Depur S.P.A, San Romano, Pisa, Italy (43°41'44.5" N, 10°46'2.7" E) on the December 23, 2022. The water pH was 9.0 and the salinity was 10‰. The original samples were maintained in Petri dishes in an incubator at a temperature of 19 ± 1 °C, using filtered artificial 10‰ marine water (Read Sea Salt, Red Sea). The WUP of *P. erythrina* was collected on the 17th October 2018, by sampling the water around the macrophytes and stones from the East Lake Wuhan, China (30°32'48"N; 114°21'14"E). The water salinity was 0‰ and the temperature was 21 °C. The specimens were cultivated in Petri dishes at about 25 °C in mineral water (Volvic, France) enriched with sterile rice grains to stimulate the growth of bacteria as food for the ciliates.

Living cells were observed and measured using bright field and differential interference contrast microscopy at a 40–1000× magnification. To highlight the ciliature and the nuclear apparatus, protargol staining was performed after Bouin's fluid fixation (Wilbert, 1975), using protargol powder made according to Pan et al. (2013). Protargol-stained cells were also used to collect meristic and morphometric data on the two populations. In the context of ITP, normal-sized cells, i.e., cells with

sizes similar to those reported for GUP by Chen et al. (2011), could be distinguished from giant cells (i.e., abnormally large cells relative to the species' typical size) solely in vivo, because protargol staining caused some cells to inflate variably, making it challenging to tell them apart.

Based on the in vivo difference in body size and cell color, we described the morphology of normal-sized and giant cells separately (see Results section). Moreover, within the normal-sized cell category, a variation in cell width, a common phenomenon in ciliate populations, was recorded. To explore whether these cell size variants represented distinct morphs, we further subdivided normal-sized cells into narrow and wide morphs. These two categories of individuals were analysed together with giants, but to avoid biases in statistical analyses of cell morphometry, the morphological data, based on living and protargol-stained cells, were collected from specimens previously distributed into three separate groups (i.e., the normal-sized cells subdivided into narrow and wide morphs, plus the giants), with each group containing 21 specimens (Table 1). Additionally, we included 50 individuals that were not artificially separated prior to staining, along with 21 specimens for each morph, resulting in a total of 113 specimens, which are referred to as “aggregated data” in Table 1.

In the WUP, giants appeared after approximately two weeks of cultivation in the laboratory, but unfortunately, we could only obtain data from the living cells, as during the protargol staining process, the giants either ruptured or failed to display infraciliature due to bleaching issues. Therefore, the meristic and morphometric data of WUP were collected exclusively from normal-sized individuals (Table 2).

Counts and measurements of ITP and WUP cells were conducted at a magnification of 1000× using a Nikon H550S microscope (Tokyo, Japan) and an Olympus BX53 compound microscope (Tokyo, Japan), respectively. Drawings were made using photomicrographs as templates. The terminology used is according to Berger (2006).

2.2. Discriminant analysis

The software Statistics 8.0 (Statsoft, Tulsa, USA) was used to analyze the experimental morphological data through discriminant analysis, a procedure of multivariate statistics. Five groups were analysed: WUP (21 specimens), three ITP morphs (21 specimens each, giving a total of 63 specimens) and an ITP mixture (50 specimens, without preliminary separation in vivo). The 20 independent variables (characters) used in the analyses are marked with asterisks in Tables 1 and 2. Due to the absence of six characters in WUP (i.e., extra frontal cirri; parabuccal cirri; cirri in left marginal row II, III, IV, V), we treat the number of these variables as 0: for instance, all 21 samples of WUP exhibit 0 extra frontal cirri, which are consequently incorporated into the analyses.

2.3. Amplification of DNA and molecular phylogenetic analyses

A single cell of ITP of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* was picked out from an overnight-starved culture, washed three times in distilled water, and put into PBS buffer. The cell was then transferred into a 0.2 mL tube (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) together with 4 µL of PBS. Total DNA material was amplified via the Whole Genome Amplification (WGA), using REPLI-g Single Cell Kit (QIAGEN®, Hilden, Germany), following the manufacturer's instructions.

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was performed in a C1000™ Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad, Hercules, USA). The almost full-length of the 18S rDNA was amplified using the primers 18S F9 (5'-CTGGTTGATCCTGCCAG-3') (Medlin et al., 1988) and 18S R1513 Hypo (5'-TGATCCTTCYGCAGGTTTC-3') (Petroni et al., 2002). High-fidelity Takara Ex Taq PCR reagents were employed (Takara Bio Inc., Otsu, Japan) according to the manufacturer's instructions. PCR cycles were set as follows: 3 min 94 °C, 35 × [30 s 94 °C, 30 s 55 °C, 2 min 72 °C], 6 min 72 °C. PCR products were purified with the EUROGOLD Cycle-Pure Kit (EuroClone, Milan, Italy) and subsequently sent to an external sequencing company (GATC Biotech AG, European Custom Sequencing

Table 1
Morphometric characterization of the Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina*.

Characters ^a	Morphs	Min	Max	Mean	Med	SD	CV	N
Body length ^b	NM	195	296	256.8	261	25.2	9.8	21
	WM	221	294	248.8	243	22.5	9.0	21
	GS	275	388	319.3	312	29.5	9.2	21
	AG	185	388	269.6	266	42.0	15.6	113
Body width ^b	NM	46	108	75.1	79	18.4	24.5	21
	WM	63	126	88.0	82	16.6	18.9	21
	GS	71	150	121.6	125	17.6	14.5	21
	AG	46	154	93.5	91	26.1	27.9	113
Body length/width, ratio	NM	2	6	3.6	4	1.0	28.5	21
	WM	2	4	2.9	3	0.7	22.2	21
	GS	2	4	2.7	3	0.4	16.7	21
	AG	2	6	3.1	3	0.8	25.9	113
Adoral zone, length ^b	NM	55	101	84.4	83	10.6	12.6	21
	WM	67	107	85.3	85	11.1	13.1	21
	GS	88	137	110.9	114	14.5	13.0	21
	AG	55	137	92.9	91	16.5	17.8	113
Adoral zone length/Body length, ratio (%)	NM	28	38	32.9	34	3.0	9.1	21
	WM	28	45	34.4	34	4.4	12.9	21
	GS	27	44	34.8	35	4.2	12.1	21
	AG	26	48	34.6	34	4.6	13.2	113
Adoral membranelles (n) ^b	NM	47	71	56.1	55	5.2	9.2	21
	WM	55	75	66.3	66	5.4	8.2	21
	GS	65	93	74.5	72	6.2	8.3	21
	AG	47	93	66.1	68	8.9	13.5	112
Frontal cirri (n) ^b	NM	12	18	15.1	14	1.6	10.7	21
	WM	14	18	15.7	16	1.5	9.3	21
	GS	14	20	16.6	16	2.3	13.8	21
	AG	12	20	15.9	16	1.9	11.9	113
Extra frontal cirri (n) ^b	NM	0	4	1.9	2	1.4	74.8	21
	WM	0	4	1.8	2	1.4	79.4	21
	GS	0	5	2.0	2	1.6	83.3	21
	AG	0	6	1.9	2	1.6	83.7	113
Buccal cirri (n) ^b	NM	1	3	1.6	2	0.6	38.0	21
	WM	1	4	2.0	2	0.8	38.7	21
	GS	1	4	2.0	2	0.9	42.2	21
	AG	0	4	1.8	2	0.8	46.9	113
Parabuccal cirri (n) ^b	NM	0	3	0.9	1	1.1	120.6	21
	WM	0	4	1.8	2	1.3	73.4	21
	GS	0	6	2.1	2	1.5	68.1	21
	AG	0	6	1.7	2	1.4	82.9	113
Frontoterminal cirri (n) ^b	NM	0	4	2.9	3	0.8	28.6	21
	WM	2	5	3.0	3	0.6	21.1	21
	GS	2	5	3.1	3	1.0	33.7	21
	AG	0	5	2.9	3	0.8	28.4	113
Midventral pairs with two cirri (n) ^b	NM	13	27	20.6	21	4.3	21.0	21
	WM	12	35	23.5	22	5.5	23.6	21
	GS	17	34	24.5	24	4.7	19.0	21
	AG	12	35	23.5	23	5.3	22.7	111
Midventral pairs with more than two cirri (n) ^b	NM	5	22	10.7	9	4.8	44.8	21
	WM	6	22	13.9	13	4.3	30.7	21
	GS	9	25	16.5	16	4.4	26.4	21
	AG	0	30	13.4	13	5.4	40.5	111
Midventral pairs, total (n)	NM	26	36	31.2	31	2.8	9.0	21
	WM	26	52	37.4	36	5.4	14.3	21
	GS	35	50	41.0	40	3.8	9.2	21
	AG	18	52	36.8	37	5.8	15.8	109
Left marginal rows (n) ^b	NM	1	3	2.1	2	0.7	33.4	21
	WM	1	3	2.1	2	0.7	33.4	21
	GS	1	5	2.5	2	0.9	35.3	21
	AG	1	5	2.3	2	0.9	39.5	113
Cirri in left marginal row I (n) ^b	NM	37	66	49.6	49	8.4	17.0	21
	WM	47	76	59.5	57	8.4	14.2	21
	GS	48	82	68.4	68	8.6	12.6	21
	AG	37	83	58.9	59	10.7	18.1	113
Cirri in left marginal row II (n) ^b	NM	8	59	30.7	32	15.9	51.7	17
	WM	5	55	17.9	12	15.5	86.5	17
	GS	8	72	30.0	25	18.5	61.6	20
	AG	2	72	22.8	19	16.5	72.2	92
Cirri in left marginal row III (n) ^b	NM	15	53	36.8	36	14.1	38.2	6
	WM	14	41	26.0	25	11.1	42.6	6
	GS	19	59	43.3	49	16.6	38.4	8
	AG	6	59	30.4	28	15.9	52.2	42
Cirri in left marginal row IV (n) ^b	GS	43	55	49.0	49	8.5	17.3	2
	AG	24	55	42.3	44	9.9	23.4	7

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Characters ^a	Morphs	Min	Max	Mean	Med	SD	CV	N
Cirri in left marginal row V (<i>n</i>) ^b	GS	39	39	39.0	39	–	–	1
	AG	13	39	30.3	39	15.0	49.5	3
Cirri in right marginal row (<i>n</i>) ^b	NM	55	89	70.1	69	10.0	14.2	21
	WM	55	84	72.9	76	8.5	11.6	21
	GS	78	104	88.0	87	6.6	7.5	21
	AG	49	104	77.2	78	11.7	15.2	113
Transverse cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	NM	0	5	3.0	3	1.2	39.4	21
	WM	2	4	3.2	4	0.9	27.5	21
	GS	0	5	3.0	3	1.1	36.7	21
	AG	0	5	3.1	3	1.1	36.8	113
Dorsal kineties (<i>n</i>) ^b	NM	3	5	4.1	4	0.7	17.1	21
	WM	3	5	4.1	4	0.7	17.1	21
	GS	3	7	4.5	4	0.9	20.7	21
	AG	3	7	4.1	4	0.8	18.4	113
Macronuclear nodules (<i>n</i>)	AG	104	178	140.5	141	24.2	17.2	21
Micronuclei (<i>n</i>)	AG	4	13	7.9	8	2.2	28.5	21
Micronuclei length	AG	5	9	6.3	6	1.2	18.8	21
Micronuclei width	AG	3	7	4.2	4	0.8	19.5	21

Normal-sized cells are subdivided into narrow morph (NM, first line) and wide morph (WM, second line); giant specimens (GS) and the aggregated data (AG) of the Italian population are reported in the third and the fourth line respectively. Note that the AG also includes 50 additional individuals that were not divided into different groups according to their in vivo cells size before protargol staining.

Abbreviations: CV, coefficient of variation in %; M, Median; Max, maximum; Mean, arithmetic mean; Min, minimum; *n*, number of corresponding characters; N, number of specimens measured; SD, standard deviation.

^a All data are based on protargol-stained specimens; measurements are in μm .

^b Data used for the discriminant analysis.

Table 2

Morphometric characterization of the Wuhan population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina*; only data for normal-sized cells were recorded.

Characters ^a	Min	Max	Mean	Med	SD	CV	N
Body length ^b	156	255	208.1	205	22.2	10.7	21
Body width ^b	51	93	70.7	68	12.1	17.1	21
Body length/width, ratio	2	4	3.0	3	0.4	12.9	21
Adoral zone, length ^b	55	78	67.9	69	6.4	9.4	21
Adoral zone length/Body length, ratio (%)	27	40	32.8	32	3.0	9.3	21
Adoral membranelles (<i>n</i>) ^b	38	53	45.0	45	4.1	9.1	21
Frontal cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	9	14	11.3	11	1.2	10.9	21
Buccal cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	1	1	1.0	1	0.0	0.0	21
Frontoterminal cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	2	2	2.0	2	0.0	0.0	21
Midventral pairs with two cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	9	31	24.0	25	5.6	23.2	21
Midventral pairs with more than two cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	0	9	2.0	1	2.8	136.8	21
Midventral pairs, total (<i>n</i>)	18	32	26.0	27	4.3	16.7	21
Left marginal rows (<i>n</i>) ^b	1	1	1.0	1	0.0	0.0	21
Cirri in left marginal row (<i>n</i>) ^b	35	55	44.0	44	5.7	12.9	21
Cirri in right marginal row (<i>n</i>) ^b	32	59	48.3	50	6.2	12.9	21
Transverse cirri (<i>n</i>) ^b	0	2	1.3	2	0.8	59.7	21
Dorsal kineties (<i>n</i>) ^b	3	4	3.2	3	0.4	13.5	21
Bristles in dorsal kinety 1 (<i>n</i>)	23	37	30.8	31	3.4	11.1	21
Bristles in dorsal kinety 2 (<i>n</i>)	16	35	25.9	27	4.8	18.6	21
Bristles in dorsal kinety 3 (<i>n</i>)	19	35	27.5	28	4.4	16.1	21
Bristles in dorsal kinety 4 (<i>n</i>)	22	32	26.4	25	4.0	15.3	5
Macronuclear nodules (<i>n</i>)	75	115	93.5	92	11.6	12.4	21
Micronuclei (<i>n</i>)	1	6	4.0	4	1.7	41.8	11
Micronuclei length	5	8	6.4	7	0.8	12.1	13
Micronuclei width	3	4	3.4	4	0.3	10.2	13

Abbreviations: CV, coefficient of variation in %; M, Median; Max, maximum; Mean, arithmetic mean; Min, minimum; *n*, number of corresponding characters; N, number of specimens measured; SD, standard deviation.

^a All data are based on protargol-stained specimens; measurements are in μm .

^b Data used for the discriminant analysis.

Centre, Germany) for direct Sanger sequencing by adding appropriate internal primers 18S R536, 18S F783, and 18S R1052 (Nittla et al., 2019).

Single cells (two in total) of WUP of *P. erythrina* were isolated with micropipettes and washed five times in sterile water. Genomic DNA was extracted using a DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The 18S rDNA sequence was amplified using the universal primers 18S-F (5'-AACCTGGTT-GATCCTGCCAGT-3') and 18S-R (5'-TGATCCTTCTGCAGGTTACCTAC-3') (Medlin et al., 1988). PCR products were purified with the MagBeads DNA Purification Kit (Genecreat Biotech, China). For confirmation, each of these two PCR products was inserted into the pEASY-Blunt E1 Expression vector using the pEASY-Blunt E1 Expression Kit (TransGen Biotech, China), and two clones of each PCR product were selected and sequenced in Wuhan Icongene Biological Technology Co., Ltd (Wuhan, China). All four sequenced clones were identical.

2.4. Whole genome assembly

The PCR products obtained according to section 2.3, were processed with a Nextera XT library and sequenced at Admera Health (South Plainfield, USA), using Illumina HiSeq X technology to generate 39,457,320 reads (paired-ends 150 bp). Preliminary assembly of resulting reads was performed using SPAdes software version 3.6.0 (Bankevich et al., 2012).

2.5. Mitochondrial genome assembly and annotation

Contigs representing the mitochondrial genome of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* were identified inside the preliminary assembly through BLAST analyses, using other hypotrichid mitochondrial genomes as references. Subsequently, based on the BLAST results, all contigs with a GC content ranging from 35 to 43 and a coverage between 200X and 400X were selected. Reads mapping on these contigs were chosen from the raw data and were reassembled using the SPAdes software to obtain the complete mitochondrial genome in a single contig. The assembled mitochondrial genome was annotated using PROKKA 1.10 (Seemann, 2014), setting the DNA translation codon table "4" and in parallel with GeneMark web tool (Besemer and Borodovsky, 2005). The results of the two tools were manually checked and open reading frames (ORFs) were considered correct when present in both tools or when showing homology with other ciliate mitochondrial proteins.

2.6. Phylogenetic and phylogenomic analyses

To analyze the phylogenetic position of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* within Kentrurostylida, we selected 84 18S rDNA sequences of members of the subclass Hypotrichia along with nine sequences of ciliates of the subclasses Oligotrichia and Choreotrichia as the outgroup (Table S1). The 18S rDNA sequences of the two *P. erythrina* populations were aligned to this species selection with the automatic aligner of the ARB software package version 5.5 (Westram et al., 2011) on the SSU ref NR99 SILVA database (Quast et al., 2012). After manual editing, a positional filter was applied to the multi-alignment of the selected species to retain only columns in which the most conserved base was present in at least 5% of the sequences. The resulting matrix was composed of 1581 columns, and the optimal substitution model was selected with jModelTest 2.1 (Darrriba et al., 2012), according to the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). Using PHYML software version 2.4 (Guindon and Gascuel, 2003) from the ARB package, a maximum likelihood (ML) tree was calculated, performing 1000 pseudo-replicates. On the same dataset a Bayesian inference (BI) tree was inferred with MrBayes 3.2 (Ronquist et al., 2012), using three runs each with one cold and three heated Monte Carlo Markov chains, with a burn-in of 25%, iterating for 1,000,000 generations. The systematic classification follows Adl et al. (2019) and Paiva (2020).

For the phylogenetic analysis based on the whole mitochondrial genome content, the amino acidic sequences of all hypotrich mitochondrial genomes deposited in the NCBI repository were downloaded. To this data set, we added our sequence, the sequence of the oligotrich *Strombidium sulcatum*, and the sequences of few selected representatives of Euplotia which were used as the outgroup. A set of 17 protein coding genes present in all the analysed genomes was selected. The orthologs were aligned using MAFFT v 7.45 (Katoh and Standley, 2013) and then concatenated together to obtain a final matrix composed of 6625 sites for each organism. The best substitution model was estimated using ProtTest3 (Darrriba et al., 2011). RAxML (Stamatakis, 2014) was used to estimate the ML phylogeny with 1000 bootstraps.

3. Results

Order da Paiva, 2020.

Family Pseudokeronopsidae Borror and Wicklow, 1983.

Genus *Pseudokeronopsis* Borror and Wicklow, 1983.

Pseudokeronopsis erythrina Chen et al., 2011.

3.1. The Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* (ITP)

(Figs. 1–4; Table 1)

Voucher material: Three voucher slides (registration number: XWX2021122301/1–3) with protargol-stained cells have been deposited in the collection of the Museo di Storia Naturale dell'Università di Pisa (Calci, Pisa, Italy); a black circle on the cover glass shows the position of the specimens of normal-sized and giant cells.

Morphology: In raw samples and during laboratory cultivation, the ITP of *P. erythrina* consistently exhibited both normal-sized and giant specimens that were easily distinguishable in vivo. We enumerated the normal-sized and giant cells out on a total of 46 and 60 individuals found on protargol slides prepared from raw samples and cultures, respectively. In the raw samples, giants comprised approximately 21.7% of the population, increasing to 26.7% during cultivation. The morphological description of these two subpopulations with the corresponding data follows.

Morphology of normal-sized cells (Table 1, first two lines): Cell size about 175–245 × 28–52 μm in vivo (10 cells measured) and 195–294 × 46–126 μm after protargol staining. Length to width ratio approximately 4.0–6.8:1 in vivo and 2–6:1 after protargol staining. Body slender-elliptical, anterior end rounded or slightly narrowed, posterior end usually narrowed, left margin conspicuously convex and right margin straight or sigmoidal; body remarkably flexible (Fig. 1A–D). Body dark reddish at low magnification due to the presence of pigmented cortical granules. Two kinds of cortical granules: type 1, orange-reddish, spherical, 0.6–0.8 μm in diameter, distributed mainly along ventral cirral rows and generally grouped in a rosette-like pattern around the dorsal cilia (Fig. 1E–G, arrows), except for some that are randomly positioned; these are responsible for the dark reddish color of the cell. Type 2, colorless and blood cell-shaped, about 1.2–1.5 μm long, densely distributed and positioned more deeply beneath cell surface than type one (Fig. 1E–G, arrowheads). Two contractile vacuoles at left margin, about 15 μm in diameter at the end of diastole, located 20% and 75% down length of body, respectively (Fig. 1A–C, arrows). Numerous lipid droplets (about

Fig. 1. Photomicrographs of the Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* in vivo (A–H, normal cells; I–L, giant cells).

A: Ventral view of a representative specimen, arrow shows contractile vacuole. B, C: A slightly compressed cell, to show the position of two contractile vacuoles. D: Lateral view showing the flexibility of the cell. E–G: Ventral (E) and dorsal (F, G) views, arrowheads show colorless blood-cell-shaped cortical granules which are irregularly distributed throughout the body, arrows indicate the grouped orange-reddish granules which are arranged along the cirral rows and dorsal kineties. H: Ventral view of buccal area. I, J: Ventral views of the giant cells, arrow indicates the non-contractile vacuole, double arrowheads mark the buccal vertex. K: Ventral view, showing the arrangement of orange-reddish granules, arrowheads mark five left marginal rows. L: Dorsal view, arrow shows a longitudinal row of densely grouped cortical granules. Scale bars: 100 μm in A–C, I, J, 50 μm in D, K, 30 μm in H, L, 20 μm in E, F.

Fig. 2. Photomicrographs of the Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* after protargol staining (A–E) and scanning electron microscopy (F–H).

A–C: Ventral (A, C) and dorsal (B) views of representative individuals, showing infraciliature, arrows indicate the buccal cirri, arrowheads in B show three dorsal kineties, double arrowheads in A and C mark the gap in adoral zone membranelles and transverse cirri, respectively. D: Ventral view of a giant cell, arrowheads indicate the segments of left marginal rows. E: Ventral view of a giant cell, showing a specimen with five left marginal rows (arrowheads), arrow indicates frontoterminal cirri, double arrowheads mark transverse cirri. F–H: Ventral (F, H) and dorsal (G) views of representative individuals, showing infraciliature, double arrowheads in I and J mark parabuccal cirri and the posterior end of paroral membrane respectively, arrowhead indicates the extra frontal cirri, arrows in J and K show two left marginal rows and four dorsal kineties, respectively. Scale bars: 50 μm in A–G, 30 μm in H.

Fig. 3. Photomicrographs of detailed views of the Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* after protargol staining (A–E, interphase cells; F–H, cells during ontogenesis).

A–C, E: Ventral views of the anterior portion, showing the variation of the frontal field structure, arrowheads show extra frontal cirri, double arrowheads show the vestigial parent right marginal row, arrows mark frontal terminal cirri, dashed lines highlight the parabuccal cirri. D: Cannibalism phenomenon, arrows indicate the anterior part of the ingested prey cell. F: Dorsal view of a middle divider, arrowheads show two dorsal kineties anlagen which develop from one old dorsal kinety. G: Ventral view of a middle-late divider, arrows show two left marginal anlagen which develop from one old left marginal row. H: Ventral view of a late divider, arrows show newly formed buccal cirri, double arrowheads mark the vestigial parent right marginal row. EFC, extra frontal cirri; MC, midventral complex; PBC, parabuccal cirri. Scale bars: 50 μm in A–E, G, H, 30 μm in F.

0.9–2.2 μm across), usually positioned in the posterior region of the cell.

Macronuclear nodules numerous (104–178), each about 5–14 μm in length; 4–13 oval micronuclei visible after protargol staining (Fig. 4B).

Three to five, usually four, dorsal kineties extending almost along the entire cell length (Fig. 2B–H, 4B).

Zero to five frontoterminal cirri close to the distal end of the adoral zone of membranelles (Fig. 4A, C–I). Twelve to 18 frontal cirri arranged in two arcs forming a “bicornona”, which connects to the midventral

complex consisting of 26–52 cirri pairs, 5–22 of which (mostly in the posterior portion) comprises groups of more than two cirri; in addition, 0–4 extra frontal cirri are present at the frontal area in some specimens (Figs. 2G and 4F,G,I). Zero to five transverse cirri arranged obliquely at some distance from the end of the midventral complex (Figs. 2C and 4C,D, double arrowheads), with cilia about 11 μm long in vivo, protruding beyond the posterior margin of the cell. Invariably one right marginal row consisting of 55–89 cirri; only a minority of the population

Fig. 4. Morphology of Italian population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* after staining with protargol (A–K), showing its high plasticity. A–D: Normal-sized individuals, ventral (A, C) and dorsal (B) views, arrows indicate the buccal cirri, arrowheads in B mark micronuclei, shaded areas show frontal cirri, the extra frontal cirri in A and parabuccal cirri in C are circled. D, E: Ventral views of giant individuals, arrows in E indicate the chaotic arrangement at the posterior end of midventral cirri, arrowheads mark the segments of left marginal cirri. F–I: Variation of buccal field infrastructure, showing different combinations of buccal cirri, parabuccal cirri, frontoterminal cirri and extra frontal cirri. J, K: Variation in the arrangement of left marginal rows. AZM, adoral zone of membranelles; DK, dorsal kineties; e, endoral membrane; FTC, frontoterminal cirri; LMR1–5, left marginal row; MC, midventral complex; p, paroral membrane; RMR, right marginal row; TC, transverse cirri. Scale bars: 50 μ m.

exhibiting vestigial parental structures in the rightmost column (Figs. 3A and 4F). One to three left marginal rows: left marginal row I comprises 37–76 cirri, left marginal rows II and III relatively shorter, consisting of 8–59 and 14–53 cirri, respectively; marginal cirri approximately 10 μ m long in vivo (Figs. 2G and 4A, C–E, J, K).

Adoral zone question mark-shaped, occupying 28–45% of cell length after protargol staining, composed of 47–75 membranelles, divided into two parts by an inconspicuous gap (Fig. 2A). The distal end of the adoral zone membranelles extends to the right margin of the cell and bends posteriad; cilia of the anterior membranelles about 14 μ m in length. Paroral membrane about half the length of the endoral (Figs. 2G and 4A). One to four buccal cirri located to the right of the paroral membrane, with 0–4 parabuccal cirri nearby (Fig. 4C, F–I).

Locomotion by slowly crawling on the substrate or by swimming while rotating about the main cell axis.

Morphology of giants (Table 1, the third line): Compared to normal-sized cells, giants are obviously different in the following aspects: (1) body shape and size, as they are much plumper, about 220–290 \times

80–125 μ m in vivo (10 cells measured), 275–388 \times 71–150 μ m after protargol staining; (2) dark red cell color, as they have more cortical granules, which are also less orange in tone (Fig. 1L); (3) some cells contain a large, likely non-contractile vacuole at the posterior end, as no expulsion process has ever been observed. (Fig. 1I); typical contractile vacuole(s) not observed; (4) presence of a higher number of dorsal kineties (3–7 vs. 3–5); (5) presence of a higher number of left marginal rows (1–5 vs. 1–3); (6) presence of a higher number of extra frontal cirri and parabuccal cirri (0–5 vs. 0–4; 0–6 vs. 0–4); (7) occurrence of cannibalism (Fig. 3D). For more details, see Table 1.

Morphogenesis during binary fission: A detailed analysis of the morphogenetic process was carried out by Chen et al. (2011) on the Guangdong population (GUP) of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina*. In the ITP population, a consistent ontogenesis pattern was observed between normal-sized and giant cells, which was also similar to the originally described one (type population) with four noteworthy differences listed below. (1) Two left marginal anlagen (LMA) can develop from one old left marginal cirral row (Fig. 3G). (2) In some cells, two dorsal kineties

anlagen (DKA) appear within one old structure and stretch toward both cell ends (Fig. 3F); these two characteristics determine the variations in the number of left marginal rows and dorsal kineties. (3) During middle-late stage, several anterior streaks of frontoventral transverse cirral anlagen divide into three segments, with the first two forming frontal cirri and the last segment developing into buccal cirri, extra frontal cirri, and parabuccal cirri. The middle streaks divide into two segments to form the midventral complex. The posterior streaks usually generate 3–5 cirri (Fig. 3G and H); this determines the variation in buccal cirri number, the presence of extra frontal cirri, parabuccal cirri, more than two cirri in the midventral pairs, and transverse cirri. (4) In a minority of cells, the vestigial parent right marginal row was not fully absorbed, causing the formation of a short extra cirral row (Fig. 3A–H, double arrowheads).

3.2. The Wuhan population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* (WUP) (Figs. 5 and 6; Table 2)

Voucher material: Eight voucher slides with protargol-stained specimens have been deposited in the Laboratory of Protozoology, Ocean University of China, China, with registration numbers XWX2018101701/1–8.

Morphology of the normal-sized cells (Table 2): Cell size about $130\text{--}210 \times 30\text{--}60 \mu\text{m}$ in vivo and $156\text{--}255 \times 51\text{--}93 \mu\text{m}$ after protargol staining. Length to width ratio approximately 3.5–5:1 in vivo and 2–4:1 after protargol staining. Usually elongated elliptical in shape with both ends rounded or narrowed; dorsoventrally flattened, with dorsal side conspicuously evidently convex at middle portion; cell remarkably flexible (Fig. 5A). Normal-sized cells exhibit an orange-reddish cell body, with a colorless cytoplasm. Two types of cortical granules visible: type 1 orange-reddish pigmented, spherical, $0.8\text{--}1.0 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, mainly distributed along ventral cirral rows and grouped in a rosette-pattern around dorsal cilia bases or scattered randomly (Fig. 5H–L); type 2 colorless, blood cell-shaped, about $1.0 \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$, densely distributed (Fig. 5G–I, J). Two contractile vacuoles located near left margin at anterior 1/3 and posterior 1/3 of the cell, $15\text{--}20 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter at the end of diastole (Fig. 5C–E). Cytoplasmic lipid droplets $1.5\text{--}2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, mainly distributed in the middle and posterior end of the cell.

Nuclear apparatus consisting of 75–115 scattered macronuclear nodules, elongated or spherical in shape, and 1–6 spherical to oval micronuclei (Fig. 6D).

Three (in 24 out of 31 specimens) or four (in 7 out of 31 specimens) dorsal kineties, extending almost the entire length of cell (Fig. 6B and C).

Fig. 5. Photomicrographs of the Wuhan population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* in vivo (A–F, bright field; G–L, differential interference contrast).

A: Ventral view of a representative specimen. **B:** Ventral view of a giant cell, arrow points to a possible ingested cell. **C–E:** Variation in shape of the body, arrows indicate the position of contractile vacuoles. **F, L:** Ventral views of compressed cells, showing orange-reddish spherical cortical granules which are grouped mainly around marginal rows and midventral complex, arrow marks the left marginal row. **G:** Ventral view, showing colorless blood-cell-shaped cortical granules which are densely and irregularly distributed throughout the body. **H, K:** Dorsal views of compressed cells, showing the grouped orange-reddish granules which are arranged along the dorsal kineties. **I, J:** Arrows indicate orange-reddish cortical granules, arrowheads indicate colorless cortical granules. **M:** Ventral view of a giant cell, showing a denser distribution of cortical granules, arrow indicates the single left marginal row. Scale bars: $50 \mu\text{m}$ in A–H, $10 \mu\text{m}$ in I, J, $20 \mu\text{m}$ in K, L, $30 \mu\text{m}$ M.

Two frontoterminal cirri close to the distal end of adoral zone of membranelles (Fig. 6E, arrows). 9–14 frontal cirri arranged in a bicorona, connecting with 18–32 pairs of midventral cirri, some of which contain three or four cirri (Fig. 6A–G, H). Usually two transverse cirri, although some individuals (4 out of 23) have no transverse cirri. One right and one left marginal row, left row with 35–55 cirri extending to posterior end of the cell, right row with 32–59 cirri arranged in an approximately J-shape, cirri about $11 \mu\text{m}$ long in vivo (Fig. 6A).

Adoral zone of membranelles about 30% of body length, comprising 38–53 membranelles, with distal end bending posteriorly onto right ventral side (Fig. 6A–E). Paroral membrane about half length of endoral membrane, with a single buccal cirrus at the right of paroral membrane (Fig. 6F).

Movement slow, by crawling on substrate or by swimming while rotating about the long body axis.

After two weeks of cultivation in nutrient-rich medium in Petri dishes, giants were observed within the cell population alongside normal-sized cells, accounting for approximately one-tenth of the total population. Giants and normal-sized cells primarily differed in size in vivo (Fig. 5B). A few relevant cell details that can roughly illustrate the morphology of giants are provided below.

Morphology of giants that emerged during cell cultivation: Most of the morphological features described for the normal-sized cells can also be attributed to giants. Interestingly, despite the very different sizes (see below), WUP giants retain the single left marginal row observed in normal-sized cells, while this character diverges between giants and normal-sized cells in the ITP (Fig. 1K).

Compared to normal-sized cells, giants differ only in three aspects: (1) a much plumper body shape, with a size of about $220\text{--}325 \times 60\text{--}130 \mu\text{m}$ in vivo (10 cells measured) (Fig. 5B); (2) denser, more abundant, and more tightly arranged cortical granules (Fig. 5M); (3) their cannibalistic behavior towards normal-sized individuals (arrow in Fig. 5B shows an ingested normal-sized cell inside a giant cell).

Morphogenesis during binary fission: The process in the WUP closely resembles that of the original population from Guangzhou (Chen et al., 2011), but with two differences: (1) during middle and late stages, streaks of frontoventral transverse cirral anlagen divide into two segments (cirri) except for several posterior streaks, which usually generate 3 or 4 cirri each (Fig. 6J and K); (2) some cells exhibit the appearance of two DKA within a single old structure, which extend towards both ends (Fig. 6N). These two characteristics result in more than two cirri in midventral pairs and four dorsal kineties, respectively. It is noteworthy that our study revealed a previously unknown very early stage of the

Fig. 6. Photomicrographs of the Wuhan population of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* after protargol staining (A–H, vegetative period; I–N, morphogenetic period). A–C: Ventral (A) and dorsal (B, C) views, arrow indicates the transverse cirri, arrowheads show the three or four dorsal kineties. D: Arrowheads mark the micronuclei. E, F: Ventral views of the anterior portion, showing frontal cirri and undulating membranes, arrows indicate the two frontoterminal cirri, double arrowheads indicate the buccal cirrus. G, H: Ventral views of the middle portion, showing mid-ventral complex, midventral pairs consist of two (G) or more cirri (H). I: Ventral view of a very early divider, arrow shows the anlage of the proter's frontoventral transverse cirri, arrowheads indicate the oral primordia of the opisthe. J, K: Ventral views of middle-late dividers, arrowheads mark several posterior streaks of frontoventral transverse cirral anlagen forming more than two cirri, arrows show frontoterminal cirri moving anteriorly. L–N: Dorsal views of middle dividers, arrows show three or four dorsal kineties anlagen, arrowheads show two dorsal kineties anlagen which develop from one old dorsal kinety. AZM, adoral zone of membranelles; DK, dorsal kineties; e, endoral membrane; FTC, frontoterminal cirri; LMR, left marginal row; MC, midventral complex; p, paroral membrane; RMR, right marginal row; TC, transverse cirri. Scale bars: 100 μ m in A, 50 μ m in B, C, G–N, 20 μ m in D–F.

process in which patches of basal bodies appear to the left of the parental midventral cirri below the buccal vertex forming a narrow longitudinal row, which is the anlage of the proter's frontoventral transverse cirri (Fig. 6I, arrow). The oral primordium of the opisthe is close to the left side of the parental midventral cirri, arranged in a longer longitudinal row, posterior to the parental equator (Fig. 6I, arrowhead).

3.3. Discriminant analysis (Fig. 7)

The composition and the plot of the two linear discriminant functions

Fig. 7. Discriminant analysis of 20 morphometric characters indicated with asterisks in Tables 1 and 2.

Symbols in the clusters refer to the total specimens analysed for each population: 113 specimens of ITP (blue, red, green, and pink labels) and 21 specimens of WUP (black labels). Ellipses outline 95% confidence areas. The composition and the plot of the two linear discriminant functions (Root 1 and Root 2), accounting for 84% (Root 1: 64%) of the variance of the measured or counted characters, are shown.

(Root 1 and Root 2), accounting for 84% (Root 1: 64%) of the variance of the measured or counted characters are shown in Fig. 7. In bidimensional space, the measured specimens are split into two clearly distinct clusters, with the character “number of adoral membranelles” providing the most weight to function Root 1 in separating WUP and ITP. Additionally, according to the results of discriminant analysis, the three morphotypes within the Italian group (ITP: narrow, wide, and giant morphotypes) show a narrow-wide-giants orientation in their distribution in the space of the first two discriminating functions (Root 1 and Root 2).

3.4. Mitochondrial genome (Fig. 8)

The complete mitochondrial genome of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* resulted in three separate linear contigs of 30,659 bp, 7546 bp, and 4614 bp respectively, with a GC content of approximately 25%. The three contigs have been deposited in GenBank under the accession number PQ676987. The putative order of the three contigs was established based on the synteny shared with the mitochondrial genome of the most closely related member of Kentruostylida, i.e., *Pseudourostyla cristata* (GenBank number: MH888186) (Fig. 8). Although it was not possible to reconstruct the complete mitochondrial genome in a single contig, we consider the three contigs to represent the whole mitochondrial genome given that no relevant gene is missing. Furthermore, it was not possible to find other ORFs related to mitochondria in the obtained assembly. The gene content of *P. erythrina* consists of 34 CDS (to which 26 could be assigned a functional annotation), five tRNAs, and two rRNAs. The overall genome content strongly resembles that of *Pseudourostyla cristata* with the exception of two genes (i.e., *nadh3* and *nadh6*, which seem to be absent in *P. cristata*), despite being significantly shorter than that of *P. cristata*'s. However, since the three mitochondrial fragments obtained could not be assembled into a single contig, the possibility that these two genes were simply not detected cannot be excluded.

3.5. Phylogenetic and phylogenomic analyses (Figs. 9 and 10)

The 18S rDNA sequences of the ITP (1663 bp, GC content 45.1%) and the WUP (1725 bp, GC content 44.87%) of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* have been deposited in GenBank with accession numbers PP873961 and

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of the structure of the *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* mitochondrial genome.

Colored areas indicate the syntenic regions between the mitochondrial genome of *P. erythrina* (present work) and those of the other two kentrustylids available in the NCBI database, i.e., *Pseudourostyla cristata* (MH888186) and *Urostyla grandis* (KX494929).

PP905230, respectively. The sequences are identical to each other and to that of the GUP (GenBank number: FJ775723). The topologies of the ML and BI trees are basically congruent, therefore only the ML tree is presented, with support values from both algorithms indicated at the nodes (Fig. 9). In both analyses, the two new sequences of *P. erythrina* formed a distinct cluster within the clade containing four sequences from *P. songi*, one sequence from *P. parasongi* and two sequences from *P. flava*, with maximal support (100% ML, 1.00 BI). *Pseudokeronopsis flava* occupies the basal position within this clade. *Trichototaxix marina* branches at the base of the genus *Pseudokeronopsis* (97% ML, 1.00 BI); together they are sister to a smaller clade that comprises the genera *Nothoholosticha* and *Heterokeronopsis*. In the ML tree based on 13 concatenated mitochondrial protein coding genes (Fig. 10), *Pseudokeronopsis* and *Pseudourostyla* cluster together (85%) and form a sister group to the order Sporadotrichida (95%).

4. Discussion

4.1. Comparison of the Italian and the Wuhan populations of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* with congeners and the type population

Li et al. (2017) discussed the systematics of the genus *Pseudokeronopsis* and recognized 11 valid species (*P. carnea*, *P. decolor*, *P. elongata*, *P. erythrina*, *P. flava*, *P. flavicans*, *P. multinucleata*, *P. pararubra*, *P. rubra*, *P. similis*, and *P. songi*). Later, Li and Xu (2020) described a new species, *P. parasongi*, bringing the total to 12. Among these, three species are notably distinct: *P. elongata* and *P. similis* possess unique moniliform macronuclear nodules (vs. multiple macronuclear nodules), and *P. decolor* lacks pigmented cortical granules, setting it apart from its pigmented congeners (Berger, 2006; Shi et al., 2007; Wang and Nie, 1935). Consequently, these three species are not elaborated upon in this paper.

The Italian population of *P. erythrina* (ITP) differs significantly from its congeners, notwithstanding its high morphological variability (Table 3). It has fewer than five transverse cirri and thus differs from *P. carnea*, *P. pararubra*, and *P. multinucleata* (Berger, 2006; Hu et al., 2004; Li et al., 2017; Song et al., 2006). *Pseudokeronopsis flavicans*, *P. flava*, and *P. parasongi* can be separated from ITP by their yellowish (vs. orange-reddish) cortical granules (Li and Xu, 2020; Song et al., 2002, 2004, 2006; Wirnsberger et al., 1987). Compared to ITP, *P. songi* has

fewer frontal cirri pairs (4–6 vs. 6–10) (Li et al., 2017), and *P. rubra* has a single contractile vacuole (vs. two contractile vacuoles) and more dorsal kinetics (3–8 vs. 3–5, usually 4) (Berger, 2006; Li et al., 2017).

Even though the morphometric data of ITP are highly variable (Table 1), they overlap those of the type population of *P. erythrina* (GUP) isolated from the brackish water of the Pearl River estuary, south of Guangzhou, China (Chen et al., 2011), and all other key characters, i.e., the body shape and color, the number and position of the contractile vacuoles, and the biotope (brackish), are consistent between the two (Table 3). Considering the presence of blood-cell-shaped cortical granules in ITP, we suspect that these were simply not detected in the original description of GUP as this type of granule is not conspicuous and easily overlooked. Moreover, due to the lack of TEM investigations, it is unclear whether these are granules or mitochondria. Thus, the identification of ITP as a population of *P. erythrina* is unequivocal.

The Wuhan population (WUP) also corresponds well to the description of GUP (Chen et al., 2011) in diagnostic features such as body shape, body size, the number and position of the contractile vacuoles and the pattern of the ventral ciliature (Table 3). Therefore, its identity as *P. erythrina* is not in doubt. GUP and WUP differ only in that the latter possesses an additional dorsal kinety, blood-cell-shaped granules (vs. the absence), and an orange reddish (vs. brick red) cell body color (Table 3). There are three or four (3.2 ± 0.4) dorsal kinetics in WUP specimens and invariably three in GUP (Chen et al., 2011). However, the variability of this character is a common feature in congeners, for example, it is also observed in *P. carnea* and *P. rubra* (Foissner, 1984; Hu and Song, 2001; Li and Xu, 2020; Li et al., 2017; Wirnsberger et al., 1987), and can thus be considered as inter-population variation (Table 3).

4.2. Intraspecific variation and morphological plasticity in *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina*: instability of ciliature, gigantism, and cannibalism

Pseudokeronopsis erythrina was originally described based on a Guangzhou population isolated in the Pearl River estuary, providing a combination of morphological and morphogenetic data with the 18S rDNA sequencing (Chen et al., 2011). Subsequently, various other aspects of this species were investigated, including the production of secondary metabolites, the chemical defence, and the molecular mechanisms of the

Fig. 9. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree inferred from the 18S rDNA sequences. Numbers near nodes represent ML bootstrap values and Bayesian posterior probabilities. Nodes marked with an asterisk correspond to the support not recovered in the BI tree. The scale bar corresponds to 0.02 expected substitutions per site. The newly sequenced *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* populations are indicated in red bold font.

vegetative ciliate cell (Anesi et al., 2016; Buonanno et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2020; Modeo et al, 2008) studied the secondary metabolites (lactones) produced by a strain of *P. erythrina* from the mouth of the Serchio River (Pisa, Italy), although the species identity of this strain has not been formalized (Modeo L., *person. commun.*). Therefore, apart from the original morphological description, subsequent studies had not addressed the taxonomy of *P. erythrina*. We are now filling this gap by providing the multidisciplinary description of two new populations (WUP and ITP), that showed gigantism in *P. erythrina* for the first time. Although WUP and ITP were collected in different environments (a natural one, the Wuhan East Lake, for WUP, vs an artificial one, a WWTP, for ITP) and show constancy (WUP) vs high variability (ITP) of their infraciliature, they share the presence of two major morphotypes, i.e., normal-sized and giant cells. The origin of the giants differs between the two populations (i.e., giants originate only during laboratory cultivation in WUP vs they are also found in the natural environment in ITP), and their relative abundance in cultivated populations (they account for roughly 10% of individuals in the WUP vs about 26% of individuals in the ITP). Linked to gigantism, cannibalism was also observed for the first time in *P. erythrina*, making the study of the morphologically very plastic ITP even more interesting.

According to our study, ITP can be easily separated from the two conspecific Chinese populations, i.e., WUP (present work) and GUP (Chen et al., 2011), by the following diverging features (Table 3): higher numbers of buccal cirri (0–4 vs. invariably one cirrus), parabuccal cirri (0–6 vs. 0), frontal cirri in the bicorona (12–20 vs. 8–14), extra frontal cirri (0–6 vs. 0), and left marginal rows (1–5 vs. invariably one), and a more variable number of dorsal kineties (3–7 vs. 3 or 4). Discriminant analysis clearly supports a distinction between ITP and WUP of *P. erythrina* (Fig. 7).

The most distinctive feature among the three populations is the variation in the number of left marginal rows and dorsal kineties (Table 3). Since WUP overlaps GUP in having a single left marginal row but differs in the presence of three or four dorsal kineties, a characteristic in common with ITP, we hypothesize that WUP may represent an intermediate state between GUP and ITP. The intraspecific variation of these two characteristics can be traced back to the morphogenetic process (see section “Morphogenesis during binary fission”). It is the instability in the number of LMA and DKA that leads to the intraspecific variation in the number of left marginal rows and dorsal kineties. Considering the instability of LMA and DKA, the variation of the arrangement of the buccal cirri, the presence of extra frontal cirri and parabuccal cirri, and

Fig. 10. Maximum likelihood tree inferred from the concatenated amino acid sequences of 13 selected mitochondrial protein coding genes. Numbers on each node represent bootstrap values. The scale bar corresponds to 0.2 substitutions per site. *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* (Italian population) is indicated in red bold font.

Table 3
Morphological comparison of the Italian and the Wuhan populations of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* with selected similar congeners.

Characters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Cell size ^a	185–388 × 46–154	135–210 × 30–60	120–220 × 20–50	81–351 × 56–96	140–350 × 30–50	200–300 × 40–55	208–288 × 30–90	180–350 × 50–90	200–250 × 30–40	121–336 × 20–152	160–300 × 30–70
Color of CG1	Orange reddish	Orange reddish	Dark reddish	Dark brownish/reddish	Yellowish	Yellowish	Dark reddish	Orange reddish	Yellow brownish	Dark reddish	Dark reddish
CG2	Present	Present	Absent	Present	Present	Present	Absent	Present	Present	Present	Present
CV, n.	2	2	1 or 2	1	1	1	1	1	1 or 2	1	1
Position of CV	A1/5, P1/4	A1/3, P1/3	P1/3 or A1/3, P1/3	P2/5–1/3	P2/5–1/3	A1/3	1/2	P1/3	P1/3 or A1/4, P1/3	P1/3	P1/3
AZM ^a , n.	47–93	38–53	36–61	46–79	ca. 45	ca. 55	–	45–92	25–49	38–92	45–56
FC ^a , n.	12–20	9–14	8–12	10–22	8–12	10–18	–	14–26	16–26	10–18	8–12
BC ^a , n.	0–4	1	1	1–2	1	1–2	–	1	1	0–2	1
MC > 2 ^a	Present	Present	Present	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
Multiple LMR	Present	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
TC ^a , n.	0–5	0–3	2–4	5–9	1–4	3–6	12 or 13	6–12	2–4	1–11	2–4
DK ^a , n.	3–7	3 or 4	3	5–8	3	4 or 5	–	4–8	3 or 4	3–8	3 or 4
Gigantism ^b	Present	Present	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
Habitat	10% WWTP	Freshwater lake	6.3% estuary	Marine	Marine	Marine	Marine	Marine	Marine	Marine	Marine
References	Present work	Present work	Chen et al. (2011)	Song et al. (2006); Li et al. (2017)	Song et al. (2004); Wirnsberger et al. (1987)	Song et al. (2002)	Berger (2006)	Hu et al. (2004); Li et al. (2017)	Li and Xu (2020)	Berger (2006); Li et al. (2017)	Li et al. (2017)

1, *P. erythrina* (ITP); aggregated data obtained from measured normal-sized as well as giant individuals were considered. 2, *P. erythrina* (WUP); 3, *P. erythrina* (GUP) (type species); 4, *P. carnea*; 5, *P. flava*; 6, *P. flavicans*; 7, *P. multinucleata*; 8, *P. pararubra*; 9, *P. parasongi*; 10, *P. rubra*; 11, *P. songi*.

Abbreviations: A, anterior position; AZM, adoral zone membranelles; BC, buccal cirri; CG1, pigment cortical granules (type 1); CG2, blood-cell-shaped granules (type 2); CV, contractile vacuoles; DK, dorsal kineties; FC, frontal cirri in bicorona; LMR, left marginal row; MC > 2, midventral pairs with more than two cirri; n, number; P, posterior position; TC, transverse cirri.

^a Data based on protargol-stained specimens;

^b Occurred naturally in ITP, manifested after a period of cultivation in WUP, considering the case of gigantism in WUP, the presence of giants in other congeners cannot be ruled out due to the lack of prior cultivation; – data not available; measurements in μm.

the formation of more than two cirri in the midventral pairs, we hypothesize that these morphological characteristics are associated with gigantism (Figs. 1I, J, 2D) and cannibalism (Fig. 3D). Previous studies dealing with ciliates such as *Blepharisma* spp., *Oxytricha bifaria*, and *Tetmemena polymorpha* (Omar et al., 2023; Ricci and Riggio, 1984; Rosati et al., 1988) have also shown that the ciliate infraciliature can be influenced by these phenomena.

The presence of gigantism and cannibalism in ITP may be due to the

abundance of food resources in its environment, given that in WUP, giants only emerged approximately two weeks after being cultivated in the laboratory, whereas in ITP gigantism was already present in raw samples collected from the WWTP. This kind of environment is known to be rich in organic matter, including bacteria, flagellates, and small-sized ciliates, which serve as food sources for relatively large-sized ciliates such as *P. erythrina* (Berk and Gunderson, 1993; Foissner et al., 1991, 1992; Moreira et al., 2022; Siqueira-Castro et al., 2016); thus, cells are fed and

grow well and some can develop a giant aspect with larger dimensions and, among other features, an enhanced buccal ciliature which confer them a competitive advantage in resource acquisition (Bhandary and Hirshfield, 1964; Foissner et al., 2002; Giese, 1938; Giese and Alden, 1938; Isquith, 1966; Pierce et al., 1978). This increase in size and vigor gives some individuals the ability to engulf conspecifics (cannibalism), providing them more nutrients, especially when the population density is high (Dawson, 1919; Devi, 1964; Foissner et al., 2002; Giese, 1938; Omar et al., 2023; Pierce et al., 1978; Ricci and Riggio, 1984). This may explain the presence of larger cells with an increased number of cirri and dorsal bristles (Table 3) in ITP compared to WUP and GUP. The latter two populations were isolated from natural environments, i.e., the East Lake and the Pearl River estuary, respectively, where food resources are relatively scarce, potentially limiting growth, whereas ITP was isolated from a WWTP where food resources were abundant thus conferring reproductive advantages for this population. Nevertheless, when WUP was grown in the lab in nutrient-rich culture media, the occurrence of giants coexisting with normal-sized cells was observed, although giants represented only a small proportion of the total population and their infraciliature remained stable.

Several studies have proposed that giants only appear during the declining phase of cultures as an adaptation to food depletion (Foissner et al., 2002; Foissner and O'Donoghue, 1990; Giese, 1938; Giese and Alden, 1938; Omar et al., 2023). Thus, as an alternative explanation, it cannot be excluded that sampled ITP cells were in the decline phase of their growth cycle and, in the presence of sufficient food supply during subsequent laboratory cultivation, coexisting giants and normal-sized cells were maintained. Compared to previously studied species exhibiting gigantism or other morphological variants (Dai et al., 2013; de Puytorac et al., 1992; Foissner, 2013; Kamra and Sapra, 1994; Lennartz, 1982; Omar et al., 2023; Pierce et al., 1978; Wicklow, 1988), the morphology of ITP cells is significantly more unstable with a higher plasticity. This phenomenon could be attributed to a combination of the relatively intricate infraciliature of *Pseudokeronopsis* cells and the complex, dynamic environment of the WWTP (Moreira et al., 2022; Polizzi et al., 2022).

Another possibility is the existence of an unknown population that bridges the gap between ITP and WUP, and which may possess a broader spectrum of variability, explaining the disparities observed in these two groups. This unresolved puzzle not only expands our understanding of *P. erythrina* but also opens new avenues for future research in the realms of systematic and evolutionary biology. This may include, for example, further exploration of the morphological and molecular variations within species, as well as their relationship with environmental or ecological factors. Such studies would likely contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the diversity and evolutionary history of species. The findings of the present study nevertheless emphasize the importance of integrative analyses, combining morphological and molecular data, in resolving the challenges of species identification and circumscription.

4.3. Phylogenetic position of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina*

Both phylogenetic and phylogenomic results confirmed the inclusion of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* within the Kentrostylida clade, supporting a close phylogenetic relationship with the genus *Pseudourostyla* (Figs. 9 and 10). Currently, the database available for mitochondrial genomes of kentrostylids is limited to only three sequences, making it premature to engage in an in-depth discussion based on this dataset.

Li et al. (2017) conducted a comprehensive evaluation of species identities and evolutionary relationships within the genus *Pseudokeronopsis*. The present investigation strongly supports the findings of that study. Notably, the inclusion of *P. parasongi* led to subtle changes in the relationships among *P. erythrina*, *P. songi*, and *P. flava*. In our molecular tree, *P. flava* branches early, with the other three species clustering together, whereas before the addition of *P. parasongi*, *P. songi* and *P. flava* formed a clade that was sister to *P. erythrina* (Li et al., 2017).

Unfortunately, the present 18S rDNA analysis could not resolve the species-level separation among the three *P. erythrina* populations (ITP, WUP, and GUP). We hypothesize that the presence of a more left marginal rows and dorsal kineties, a chaotic ciliature in the buccal field and the midventral complex, and the larger body size, could indicate that ITP may be undergoing a potential speciation process through a combination of adaptation to life in resource-rich habitats and cannibalism.

Our research provides 18S rDNA and genomic information for the Italian population of *P. erythrina*. However, given the lack of genomic data for other populations, relying solely on the conservative nature of 18S rDNA hindered our ability to conduct in-depth phylogenomic studies. This limitation prevented us from fully exploring the significant morphological differences observed and understanding their correlation with molecular genetic information. Accumulating more molecular data on cryptic, pseudocryptic, and complex species (Gout et al., 2023; Melekhin et al., 2022; Potekhin and Mayén-Estrada, 2020; Rataj et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2022) would doubtless help address these challenges.

4.4. Notes on the evolutionary relationships between and within the families Pseudokeronopsidae and Pseudourostylidae with a special focus on the genus *Trichototaxis*

The two families Pseudourostylidae and Pseudokeronopsidae are morphologically distinct from each other mainly in terms of the number of marginal rows: the former has multiple marginal rows, while the latter has only one right and one left row. Additionally, during morphogenesis, the macronuclear nodules of pseudourostylids fuse into a single mass, while in pseudokeronopsids, the macronuclear nodules either fuse into a single mass or divide individually (Berger, 2006; Chen et al., 2011, 2014; Li and Xu, 2020; Li et al., 2017, 2018; Shi et al., 2007). The Italian population of *P. erythrina* corresponds well with pseudokeronopsids, except for the presence of multiple left marginal rows in some cells, which is a characteristic of pseudourostylids. *Pseudokeronopsis elongata* and *P. similis* have unique features such as a moniliform macronucleus that distinguishes them from other species in the family Pseudokeronopsidae (Shi et al., 2007; Wang and Nie, 1935). Shi et al. (2007) found that *P. similis* forms a single spherical macronuclear mass at the mid-divisional stage, which is typical of the family Pseudourostylidae. Accordingly, ITP, along with *P. elongata* and *P. similis*, could be considered as an intermediate form between the family Pseudourostylidae and Pseudokeronopsidae.

The genus *Trichototaxis*, which was established by Stokes (1891) with *T. stagnatilis* as the type species by original designation, is considered a member of the family Pseudourostylidae. Its main distinguishing feature is the presence of multiple left marginal rows, however, *T. stagnatilis* has never been redescribed in detail. Only two species have been characterized using modern taxonomic methods so far, namely *T. songi* (Chen et al., 2007) and *T. marina* Lu et al. (2014), but their assignment to the family Pseudourostylidae is questionable due to their strong resemblance to *Pseudokeronopsis*. Indeed, they possess multiple left marginal rows, which is considered a key character to distinguish *Trichototaxis* from *Pseudokeronopsis*, but the discovery of multiple left marginal rows in *P. erythrina* ITP could question the assignment of *Trichototaxis* to the family Pseudourostylidae. Moreover, the macronuclear nodules of *T. songi* and *T. marina* fuse into multiple masses during morphogenesis (Lu et al., 2014; Shao et al., 2014), which contrasts with the typical pattern observed in Pseudourostylidae where the macronuclear nodules fuse into a single mass. However, the former pattern is consistent with that observed in most species of *Pseudokeronopsis*. Based on these observations, *T. songi* and *T. marina* may represent intermediate forms between Pseudourostylidae and Pseudokeronopsidae. The placement of *T. marina* at the root of the *Pseudokeronopsis* clade in our 18S rDNA tree supports this hypothesis. However, without morphogenetic or molecular data on its type species, *T. stagnatilis*, it is premature to make any conclusions about the family assignment of *Trichototaxis*.

4.5. Improved diagnosis of the genus *Pseudokeronopsis* Borror and Wicklow, 1983

Adoral zone of membranelles continuous. Frontal cirri arranged into a bicorona. Buccal cirrus present. Two or more frontoterminal cirri. Midventral complex composed of midventral pairs only, occasionally some “pairs” consist of more than two cirri each. Transverse cirri present. One or more left marginal row/s, one right marginal row, three or more dorsal kineties on average. Caudal cirri lacking. Numerous macronuclear nodules. Parental adoral zone completely replaced during division. Macronuclear nodules divide individually. Euryhaline.

4.6. Improved diagnosis of *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina* Chen et al. (2011)

Body brick- or orange-red in color, elongate and elliptical in shape, flexible and slender, measuring 120–280 × 20–85 µm in vivo (giants: 220–290 × 80–125 µm in vivo). Adoral zone continuous and composed of 36–93 membranelles. Paroral membrane much significantly shorter than endoral membrane. Eight to 20 frontal cirri forming a bicorona; 0–6 extra frontal, 0–4 buccal, 0–6 parabuccal, 0–5 frontoterminal, and 0–5 transverse cirri. Midventral complex composed of 18–52 pairs of cirri, extends to transverse cirri, posterior pairs often with more than two cirri. One or more left marginal rows, first row with approximately 35–83 cirri, one right marginal row with 32–104 cirri. 3–7 dorsal kineties. Two types of cortical granules: type 1 orange-reddish, spherical, approximately 0.8–1 µm across, grouped mainly along cirral rows and dorsal kineties, some sparsely distributed throughout body; type 2 colorless, blood-cell-shaped, densely, and irregularly distributed throughout body. Two contractile vacuoles, one located at anterior 1/3 of body, one at posterior 1/3; 53–115 macronuclear nodules.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we isolated two new populations of the well-known kentrurostylid *Pseudokeronopsis erythrina*, referred to as ITP and WUP, from a brackish WWTP and a freshwater lake, respectively. These new isolates offered an extraordinary opportunity to delve deeper into the species, enabling a multidisciplinary exploration that unveils new insights into its morphology, morphogenesis, and the variations of its ciliary structure. Additionally, we provided comprehensive genomic information detailing the species' position within 18S rDNA and phylogenetic trees. Our findings revealed a significant level of morphological plasticity among *P. erythrina* populations, including remarkable phenomena like gigantism and cannibalism. These behaviors, previously unobserved in kentrurostylids, challenge the existing criteria for species identification within the *Pseudokeronopsis* genus. Finally, our analysis of 18S rDNA attributes the high morphological plasticity observed in the ITP population to the complex and dynamic environment of the WWTP. This result highlights the critical significance of understanding the evolutionary processes that shape aquatic organisms in such intricate ecosystems, paving the way for future research in this field.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Wenxin Xu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Leandro Gammuto:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Data curation. **Valentina Serra:** Writing – review & editing. **Xiaotian Luo:** Writing – review & editing. **Fabrizio Erra:** Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Jie Huang:** Writing – review & editing. **Giulia Cerritelli:** Writing – review & editing. **Giulio Petroni:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Letizia Modeo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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